

OVERCOMING FINANCIAL OBSTACLES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Introduction

The Global Community is increasingly recognizing the urgent need to transition towards a green economy to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change, reduce pollution and promote sustainable development. This shift involves adopting environmentally-friendly practices, technologies and policies across various sectors, including energy, transportation, agriculture and construction. “Going Green “ is an economic opportunity, its heroes are “sustainable entrepreneurs”, banks and corporations.⁵

Financial institutions and industries can anticipate and mitigate potential losses related to environmental factors by evaluating and communicating climate risks and political uncertainties.⁶ The aim is to minimize environmental impact, mitigate climate change and foster long-term sustainability across various sectors. Governments, businesses and civil society are embracing renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind and hydroelectric power to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and decrease greenhouse gas emissions since the main responsibility lays in front of them. Moreover, there is a growing emphasis on energy efficiency, waste reduction, recycling and sustainable resource management to minimize environmental impact and promote circular economy principles. Addressing financial challenges is critical

⁵ *Green Growth: Ideology, Political Economy and the Alternatives*, published by ZED Books 2016, Gareth Dale, Manu V. Mathai and Jose A. Puppim de Oliver page 4

⁶ *Advancing green finance: a review of sustainable development* Chengbo Fu, Lei Lu and Mansoor Pirabi p. 19

for ensuring the success and stability of green economy initiatives. While the shift towards a green economy holds immense potential for environmental and social benefits, it also presents significant financial challenges that must be addressed to ensure sustainable progress.

The successful implementation of green initiatives requires substantial investments in infrastructure, technology, research and development. However, high upfront costs, limited access to capital and uncertain returns on investment often pose significant obstacles.

Green initiatives, particularly those focused on renewable energy and sustainable infrastructure, often necessitate substantial financial investments for several reasons. Firstly, the development of renewable energy plants, such as solar or wind farms, requires significant upfront costs for equipment, land acquisition and installation. Additionally, investments in research and development are crucial for advancing green technologies and improving their efficiency and cost-effectiveness over time. Moreover, green projects may involve long-term investments in infrastructure and systems to ensure their viability and longevity, adding to the overall capital requirements.

A successful, politically feasible and economically viable transition to the green economy requires addressing significant challenges facing many developing countries that lack the sufficient financial, technical and human capital needed to structurally transform their economies.⁷ Germany's Energiewende (Energy Transition) is a prime example of a developed country's ambitious shift towards renewable energy. The country's commitment to phasing out nuclear power and reducing greenhouse gas emissions necessitated significant capital investments.

Initiatives such as feed-in-tariffs and renewable energy subsidies played a crucial role in attracting private investment. Despite initial challenges, Germany's renewable energy sector has thrived, with renewable accounting for over 40% of the country's electricity generation. India's ambitious solar energy targets have

⁷ *Why a green economy matters for the Least Developed Countries- UNEP, p.3*

propelled it to the forefront of renewable energy development. The country's Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission aims to install 104 GW of solar capacity by 2025. To attract investment, India has implemented policies such as solar auctions and tax incentives. The success of projects like the Bhadla Solar Park in Rajasthan highlights the potential for large-scale solar deployment in developing countries.

Despite the potential long-term benefits of green projects, traditional investors often exhibit reluctance due to perceived risks and longer return on investment (ROI) periods. Green investments are typically characterized by higher upfront costs and longer payback periods compared to conventional projects, leading to concerns about financial returns and profitability. Moreover, uncertainties stemming from regulatory ambiguity, technological vulnerabilities and market fluctuations amplify investor skepticism.

Government Intervention: Policies and Solutions

Governmental organizations have to be involved in order to effectively promote the growth of the green economy. Governments play a crucial role in establishing the rules and structure required to encourage sustainable behavior. Their engagement creates an atmosphere that is favorable to innovation and investment in green initiatives, while also setting the tone for the direction of economic activities. Moreover, one of the most popular strategies used by governments to incentive people and companies to adopt eco-friendly practices is the provision of tax breaks. Governments can mitigate stakeholder financial burdens and encourage green economy involvement by providing tax advantages, such as credits or deductions, for expenses linked to energy efficiency upgrades, renewable energy purchases, or adaptation of green technologies.

The significant initial expenses of green investments are largely mitigated by subsidies, which also increase their accessibility and appeal to a wider range of investors. Government subsidies work as accelerators to speed up the shift to a greener and more sustainable future. Examples of these include financial support for

renewable energy projects, incentives for the sustainable farming methods and subsidies for the purchase of electric vehicles. Cap-and-trade systems, which entail tradable permits, present a novel means of providing incentives for reducing pollution. Governments establish a market-based framework that incentivizes firms to adopt cleaner technology and practices by capping emissions and permitting organizations to trade permits reflecting the right to emit a specific amount of pollutants. Tradable permits encourage economical carbon reductions while giving businesses flexibility in adhering to environmental laws.

Raising public knowledge of the advantages of the green economy and the significance of sustainable finance is crucial to generating demand and backing for environmentally friendly projects. Campaigns, gatherings and community outreach initiatives that can generate support from the general public and inspire people to adopt environmentally conscious decisions. Investors and financial institutions can design unique financing methods specifically suited to the requirements of green initiatives. Green bonds, venture capital funds or loan programs with advantageous terms for sustainable ventures are a few examples of this. By combining public and private resources, public-private partnerships can also make finance more accessible.

Innovative financing models, such as pay-for-success contracts and crowdfunding platforms, can mobilize funding for green projects from diverse sources. These models allow investors to fund projects based on their expected environmental and social impact, thereby attracting capital to sustainable initiatives. Capacity-building programs can help organizations and individuals acquire the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the financial landscape of the green economy. This may involve training programs, workshops and educational initiatives focused on financial literacy on financial literacy, project management and sustainable investment practices.

Clear and consistent policies give investors certainty and encourage long-term commitments to green investments. Governments can support green finance by enacting supportive policies and regulatory frameworks that foster the

sector. Examples of these include carbon pricing mechanisms, standards for sustainable finance disclosure and targets for renewable energy.

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